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Phenological Display of Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) in Salt Affected Area of South Punjab, Pakistan

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Abstract

The sunflower is a significant oilseed crop that can help reduce the disparity amid the utilization and manufacture of edible oil in developing nations such as Pakistan. Despite its potential, minimal research has been carried out on the genetic presentation of sunflower hybrids that can exhibit distinct behavior under agro-saline conditions. As a result, exploring the genetic display of sunflower hybrids that can withstand harsh environmental conditions is critical for improving agricultural productivity and addressing food insecurity challenges. The final yield of achene crops is significantly influenced by agronomic traits. As such, any improvement in these traits can lead to an increase in the yield of achene crops. To assess the performance of three different sunflower hybrids (Hysun-33, Augura 4, and S-278) under agro-saline conditions in Dera Ghazi Khan, Pakistan, a field trial was conducted at the Agronomy experimental area of the Adaptive Research Farm for two consecutive years (2017 and 2018). The randomized complete block design was employed, and each plot measured 10 x 05 m². The experiment was replicated thrice to ensure the validity of the findings. It was experimental that amongst sunflower hybrids, Hysun-33 performed best during both the years, agronomically and yield wise followed by S278 and Augura 4 in spite of severe brackish underground water and saline growing medium of experimental area. Hysun-33 hybrid produced significantly taller plants, more Head diameter, maximum Leaf area, heavier 100-achene weight and higher achene yield, but lesser oil content than these in Augura 4 and S 278 hybrids during both the years of research. It was further observed that hybrid Augura 4 remained poor in morphological as well as in reproductive traits thus depicting poor performance in all parameters except in oil contents in saline conditions for both the years. To increase productivity and cultivate saline areas, the Hysun 33 sunflower hybrid should be recommended and promoted in regions such as Dera Ghazi Khan. This hybrid has shown excellent performance in terms of plant height, head diameter, and achene yield, making it a viable option for cultivation. In particular, during the 2017 season when the crop was exposed to higher temperatures, rainfall, and solar radiation, the Hysun-33 genotype proved to be the most successful. By utilizing this hybrid, previously fallow land can be brought under cultivation, contributing to an increase in edible oil productivity and the expansion of agricultural area. These favorable environmental factors positively impacted the crop's phenology attributes and ultimately contributed towards an increased achene yield despite the challenging soil conditions of the area.

Keywords: Sunflower; Hybrids; Salt Affected Area; Phenological Traits

1. Introduction:

Pakistan, known for its agricultural prowess, is currently grappling with a cruel scarcity of edible oil

due to its low household manufacture levels, which fall significantly below the consumption rates. This has

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resulted in a considerable portion of the country's foreign exchange being expended on importing oil, which only increases annually. One potential solution to this crisis is the cultivation of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), which is a vital non-traditional oilseed and C4 crop belonging to the Asteraceae (Compositae) family. Sunflower seeds are rich in edible oil, containing approximately 39-49%, which is low in saturated and trans-fats. During a study conducted by Ryland (2003), various vegetable oils were compared, with sunflower oil being identified as the healthiest due to its elevated oleic acid satisfied. By promoting and expanding sunflower cultivation, Pakistan can potentially mitigate its dependence on imported oil and increase its domestic oil production levels, ultimately aiding the country's economy.

Pakistan, as an agricultural nation, is facing an ongoing issue of inadequate edible oil supplies. This problem has become more pronounced over the last two decades, as consumer demand for edible oil has increased from 0.30 million to 2.79 million tons (GOP, 2010), making it the largest single food import in Pakistan. One feasible solution to meet the surging demand for edible oil is to cultivate sunflower, which can be grown twice annually in Pakistan, during the spring and autumn seasons. However, the growth of sunflower during the spring season is slower than during the autumn season (Kaleem et al., 2010). To address this rising demand for edible oil in the country, there are two potential solutions: increase the area under oilseed crops, particularly non-conventional oilseed crops, or use high-yielding hybrids/varieties with advanced production technology (Shabir et al., 2010).

Sunflower is known for its broad adaptability to various soil and climatic conditions (Bakht et al., 2006). Its fibrous and long root system provides moderate tolerance to salinity, allowing it to thrive in problem soils and brackish water (Francois, 1996). Therefore, sunflower can be grown successfully in different areas of Pakistan, providing an excellent opportunity to increase the production of edible oil in the country. By taking advantage of this potential, Pakistan can become self-sufficient in edible oil production and reduce its dependence on costly imports. However, research by Genuchten & Hoffman (1993) has shown that increasing salinity levels significantly reduce seed yield in all sunflower hybrids.

Despite this, research has demonstrated that sunflower has great potential to be grown in rain-fed and irrigated farming systems under varying soil and climatic conditions (Skoric, 2016). Thus, with proper cultivation practices, sunflower could be a viable solution to Pakistan's chronic shortage of edible oil.

The performance of different genotypes can be influenced by the environment in which they are grown, with their efficacy varying according to location and season (Kaleem et al., 2010). Hybrid crops have been introduced in order to increase global production and acreage of edible oil seed crops due to their higher yield potential compared to open pollinated varieties (OPVs). In Pakistan, for example, almost all of the sunflower crops are planted with imported hybrid seeds, which can be costly and difficult to obtain in sufficient quantities and at the appropriate time (Kaleem et al., 2010).

Hybrid performance can be influenced by both genotype and environment, with differences in physiomorphic traits potentially resulting from varying environmental factors such as temperature and radiation (Khan et al., 2019). Although the effects of temperature on oil content have been found to vary, the relatively high average temperature of approximately 34°C during the period of seed development and maturation in some studies could potentially account for a lower oil content (Francois, 1996).

Sunflower farming in Pakistan typically involves using imported hybrid seeds that can be costly. However, these seeds may not be well-suited to local climatic conditions, resulting in lower yields. It is therefore crucial to assess the seeds under the appropriate environmental conditions to ensure their adaptability, growth potential, and yield capacity. Evaluating the crop's various attributes before growing it on a commercial scale is a critical part of this testing process. To enhance sunflower production in Pakistan, it may be necessary to breed new hybrid seeds that are specifically tailored to local climatic conditions (Iqrasan et al., 2017).

In this study, we tested three different sunflower hybrids to evaluate their phenological expression under agro-climatic soil conditions with saline properties and brackish underground water in southern Punjab, Pakistan (Table 1).

Table 1: Physico- chemical Properties of soil and water before sowing of crop

S. No.	Analytical report of tube well water	S. No.	Soil Characteristics
1	Electrical conductivity (EC×10 ⁶)	1	Soil Condition
2	Ca+ Mg (mg l ⁻¹)	2	Soil Texture
3	Na (mg l ⁻¹)	3	Soil pH
4	Carbonate (mg l ⁻¹)	4	EC(m S cm ⁻¹)

5	Chloride (mg l ⁻¹)	4.80	5	Organic Matter (%)	0.42
6	SAR	1.26	6	Saturation (%)	44

1.1. Objectives:

- To predict the sunflower seed and oil response to salinity.
- To verify the genetic expression and performance of locally available sunflower hybrids, especially under challenging soil and water conditions, for further assessment and testing.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Field Experiment:

A field experiment was conducted during spring 2017 and 2018 to assess the performance of 3 sunflower genotypes (Hysun-33, Augura 4 and S-278) at government Adaptive research Farm Rakh chabbri Zareen, Dera Ghazi Khan, Pakistan having saline soil and brackish underground water. To conduct the experiment, a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications was utilized. The physico-chemical properties of the soil used are summarized in Table 1. The soil pH was measured to be 8.70, the electrical conductivity was 7.66 dS m⁻¹, and the organic matter content was 0.68%. The soil texture was classified as sandy loam, while the soil condition was identified as being both saline and waterlogged. The results of the analytical report on brackish underground water (presented in Table 1) indicate an electrical conductivity of 1366 (EC x 10⁶), Na concentration of 2.93 (mg l⁻¹), Carbonate concentration of 6.06 (mg l⁻¹), Chloride concentration of 4.80 (mg l⁻¹), and SAR of 1.26. The study was conducted over a two-year period from 2017 to 2018, and the physiochemical properties of the soil and water were analyzed prior to crop sowing. The size of the net plot was 3.0 m x 5.0 m, and three sunflower hybrids (Hysun 33, Augura 4, and S-278) were carefully selected and sown on ridges with a seed rate of 8 kg ha⁻¹. The spacing between ridges and plants was maintained at 75 cm and 25 cm, respectively. These specific sunflower hybrids were chosen to cater to the demands of farmers in the region who rely heavily on them for their sunflower production. The planting of these sunflower hybrids took place during the spring season, which remained consistent for both years.

An optimal dose of fertilizer was applied to the field using urea and triple superphosphate (TSP) to promote crop growth. To promote optimal growth, a fertilizer regimen of 150 kg/ha of nitrogen and 100 kg/ha of phosphorus was employed, with half of the

nitrogen and the full dose of phosphorus administered during sowing. Subsequently, the remaining nitrogen was delivered during the first irrigation. Adequate moisture levels were ensured through four separate irrigation sessions. One plant per hill was maintained after the emergence stage to promote healthy growth, and excess plants were removed during thinning at the 2-3 leaf stage. Regular manual weeding was carried out to effectively control weeds throughout the crop's lifecycle. The first doze was applied at the 4-6 leaf stage (25 DAS), followed by the second irrigation at bud initiation (45 DAS), the third irrigation at flower initiation (67 DAS), and the fourth irrigation at grain formation (90 DAS) stage. These practices were implemented to ensure high-quality yield and healthy growth of the crop.

The research study focused on various aspects of sunflower plants, such as plant height, head diameter, leaf area, 100-achene weight, achene yield, and oil content. To ensure the accuracy of the results, ten plants were randomly selected from each plot, and data was collected and averaged. Harvesting was done manually at the time of maturity, where heads were cut using a sickle, dried in sunlight, and threshed by hand. The achene yield per plot was recorded after adjusting to 10% moisture content and then converted into kg ha⁻¹. To determine the oil yield, random samples from each plot were analysed using the Soxhlet Fat Extraction method. The study aimed to analyse the growth and productivity of sunflower plants, ensuring precision in the results obtained.

The height of the plants was evaluated by measuring from the soil surface to the top growth, including the head. At physiological maturity, the leaf area was calculated using a leaf area meter. The harvest was conducted for a duration of seven days due to differences in maturity among the hybrids. For achene yield determination, a 3.5 square meter area was harvested from the centre of each plot, and the seed heads were manually collected, weighed, and threshed. To analyse the oil content in the seeds, an Oxford 4000 NMR Spectrometer was used. This procedure was carried out to ensure accurate and reliable results. By implementing these protocols, we can obtain precise data for better understanding and management of plant growth and development.

The recorded data for each trait was analyzed using ANOVA to determine if any statistically significant differences existed among the genotypes. The study provides valuable insights into the growth and yield of sunflower plants and could aid in the development of more efficient farming practices.

According to meteorological data, temperature and rainfall played a significant role in

crop growth during the crop life cycle as shown in Fig. 1. The mean high temperatures for January and May 2017 were 27°C and 42.86°C respectively, while the mean low temperatures ranged from 7.66°C to 28.15°C. In contrast, the mean high temperatures for January and May 2018 were 23.21°C and 41.70°C, with corresponding low temperatures of 8°C and 26.60°C. The rainfall received during the 2017 crop season was 37.36mm, whereas in 2018, it was the lowest at 21.13mm. The crop received higher solar radiation in May 2017, with 24.80 compared to 23.5 in May 2018. The environmental factors such as temperature and solar radiation, can impact crop growth, affecting not only their phenology but also their physiological and qualitative characteristics. These factors can alter crop vigor, yield, and the accumulation of oil and fatty acids.

Therefore, it is essential to consider the cumulative effects of these variables to ensure optimal crop productivity and quality. By understanding these environmental influences, farmers can make informed decisions to mitigate their impact and improve overall crop performance. (Kaleem et al., 2010).

Experiments were carried out at salt affected site and before sowing of crop, a composite and representative soil sample from a depth of 32 cm was obtained with the help of soil auger in addition to tube well water sample for analyzing laboratory report. The description of physio-chemical characteristics of the experimental site for water and the soil are given in table 1. Report of these samples was collected from the soil and water testing laboratory of concerned district during study.

Figure 1: Weather graph of growing season 2017 and 2018

3. Results:

The analysis of variance showed that the statistical differences among treatment means for various parameters were achieved as depicted in Table 3. To gauge the growth characteristics of sunflower crops,

plant height stands out as a significant morphological factor. The data for plant height as described in Table 3, indicates statistical significant ($P < 0.05$) difference among treatment means during year 2017 but statistically non-significant ($P < 0.05$) difference among treatment means were received during year 2018

regarding plant height. The findings in Table 3 demonstrate that Hysun-33, a sunflower hybrid, achieved the greatest plant height of 164.17 cm. This was followed by S-278, which reached a height of 154.18 cm, and Augura 4 hybrid, which had the smallest height of 148.84 cm. These results were consistent with the plant height trends observed in 2018. Plant height and head diameter are important traits that affect the yield of sunflowers. Both genetic makeup and environmental conditions contribute to the growth of sunflowers. A study was conducted to evaluate the effect of these factors on various sunflower hybrids during two consecutive years, 2017 and 2018. The results showed that the hybrids grew taller in 2017 than in 2018 (Fig. 3), possibly due to

higher temperatures, rainfall, and intercepted solar radiation. The hybrid Hysun-33 produced the greatest head diameter of 16.43 cm in 2017, which was statistically equivalent to the head diameter of 15.21 cm achieved by the S-278 cultivar. The lowest head diameter of 13.53 cm was recorded in the Augura 4 cultivar. Similarly, in 2018, Hysun-33 produced a larger head diameter of 14.25 cm than the minimum of 12.00 cm recorded in the Augura 4 cultivar. All cultivars produced larger head diameter in 2017 compared to 2018 (Fig. 2). The difference in head diameter among different sunflower hybrids is likely due to their genetic potential, along with higher intercepted solar radiation, growing degree days, and rainfall in 2017 than in 2018.

Figure 2: Comparison of head diameter among different hybrids for two growing season 2017-18

Figure 3: Comparison of Plant height (cm) among different hybrids for two growing season 2017-18

The results presented in Table 3 indicate a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) among treatment means for Leaf during the years 2017 and 2018. Leaf area is an important attribute of sunflowers and during 2017, all genotypes accumulated a higher leaf area due to favorable weather conditions (Table 2) resulting in maximum photosynthates, compared to lesser accumulation in 2018. Among the genotypes studied, Hysun 33 produced the maximum leaf area of 2250 cm^2 in 2017, which was statistically similar to cultivar

S278 (2200 cm^2), while Augura 4 hybrid had the minimum leaf area of 1624 cm^2 . A similar trend was observed in 2018, where Hysun 33 had the maximum leaf area of 2124 cm^2 followed by Augura 4 hybrids with 1558 cm^2 (Fig. 4).

The data presented in Table 2 indicate a linear increase in leaf area with higher temperature and solar radiation. The variation in leaf area among genotypes (Fig. 4) could be attributed to the differences in genetic makeup and weather conditions.

Table 2: Mean monthly weather data during growing season of Sunflower years 2017 and 2018>

Months	Mean Max Temp °C		Mean Min Temp °C		Total rainfall (mm)		Solar radiation	
	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018
January	20.31	23.21	7.66	8.00	17.97	0.03	10.90	12.63
February	26.36	26.10	10.82	11.00	4.95	5.21	14.00	14.50
March	31.29	33.31	15.80	17.60	4.38	6.62	17.20	17.60
April	39.40	38.50	23.47	22.7	7.50	4.71	21.64	22.30
May	42.86	41.70	28.15	26.60	2.54	4.60	24.80	23.51

Table 3: Comparative performance of Sunflower years 2017 and 2018 spring season.

Hybrids	Plant Height (cm)		Head diameter (cm)		Leaf Area (Max) (cm^2)	
	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018
Hysun 33	164.17 A	151.91	16.43 A	14.25 A	2250 A	2124 A
Aguara 4	148.84 C	144.01	13.53 B	12.00 C	1624 B	1558 C
S-278	154.18 B	149.37	15.21 AB	13.14 B	2200 A	1750 B
Significant	**	NS	*	**	*	**
LSD Value	6.14	12.76	2.47	1.03	517.41	90.76

	100 Achene Weight (g)		Yield (kg/ha)		Oil Content %	
	2017	2018	2017	2018	2017	2018
Hysun 33	9.55	8.91 A	2909.00 A	2333.8 A	38.68 B	37.00 AB
Aguara 4	6.70	5.98 B	2125.10 B	1760.3 B	41.67 A	39.33 A
S-278	8.38	8.13 AB	2736.50 AB	1917.1 B	36.68 C	35.33 B
Significant	NS	*	*	**	**	*
LSD Value	3.12	2.41	645.35	280.18	1.68	3.69

Figure 4: Comparison of Max Leaf Area (cm^2) among different hybrids for two growing season 2017-18

The trait of 100-achene weight (HAW) is an important factor in determining yield, and was found to have non-significant results for the year 2017, while significant differences among hybrids were observed for the year 2018. Analysis of Table 3 shows that Hysun 33 had the highest HAW (9.55g) in the year 2017, while Augura 4 had the lowest (6.70g). Similar results were observed in the year 2018, with Hysun 33 producing the highest HAW (8.91g), which was statistically similar to S-278, which had a HAW of 8.13g. The importance of 100-achene weight in sunflowers is highlighted by its strong and positive correlation with seed yield. Sunflower hybrids were found to accumulate higher thermal units and solar interception in 2017 than in 2018 (Fig. 1), resulting in higher yield and yield components due to the accumulation of more growing degree days (GDD) and solar radiation, and thus higher HAW was recorded in 2017.

The ultimate achene yield of sunflower crops is determined by various factors, including individual yield components. Based on the findings presented in Table 3, it is evident that there were notable differences in achene yield among various sunflower hybrids over both years of study. For instance, in 2017, hybrid Hysun-33 produced the highest achene yield of 2909.00kg ha⁻¹, whereas the lowest yield of 2125.10kg ha⁻¹ was observed in Augura 4 hybrid. However, these two hybrids did not exhibit a significant difference statistically. Similar results were observed in 2018, where Hysun-33 recorded the maximum yield of 2333.8 kg ha⁻¹, followed by 1917.10kg ha⁻¹ in S-278 hybrid, and Augura 4 hybrid showed the lowest yield of 2125.10 kg ha⁻¹.

The production of aching weight and yield in hybrid sunflowers appears to be influenced by their genetics, as indicated by the variations observed in all three hybrids across the two years. In 2017, the sunflower hybrids that received greater thermal heat units, solar interception, and rainfall produced higher yields and yield components.

4. Discussion:

The present results are consistent with previous studies by Kaleem *et al.* (2010), which also observed variations in plant height of different sunflower genotypes. Additionally, the head diameter was found to be statistically significant for both years of the study. Studies by Kaleem *et al.* (2010), Goyne *et al.* (1989), Khan *et al.* (2019) and Iqrasan *et al.* (2017) have also reported that larger sunflower heads contribute to higher seed yield and yield attributes. Therefore, selecting sunflower hybrids with larger head diameter can potentially increase yield.

Leaf area is an important attribute of sunflowers and during 2017, all genotypes accumulated a higher leaf area due to favorable weather conditions (Table 2) resulting in maximum photosynthates, compared to lesser accumulation in 2018. This finding is consistent with the results of Kaleem *et al.* (2010). The data presented in Table 2 indicate a linear increase in leaf area with higher temperature and solar radiation, which is consistent with the findings of Gone *et al.* (1989) and Iqrasan *et al.* (2017), who observed that leaf area remains maximum at higher overall growth temperatures and intercepted light. The variation in leaf area among genotypes (Fig. 4) could be attributed to the differences in genetic makeup and weather conditions. This finding is consistent with the results of Kaleem *et al.* (2010). The importance of 100-achene weight in sunflowers is highlighted by its strong and positive correlation with seed yield, as reported by Iqrasan *et al.* (2017) and Brouder *et al.* (2008). Sunflower hybrids were found to accumulate higher thermal units and solar interception in 2017 than in 2018 (Fig. 1), resulting in higher yield and yield components due to the accumulation of more growing degree days (GDD) and solar radiation, and thus higher HAW was recorded in 2017. This finding is consistent with the results reported by Caliskan *et al.* (2008). The production of aching weight and yield in hybrid sunflowers appears to be influenced by their genetics, as indicated by the variations observed in all three hybrids across the two years. These results differ from those reported by Khan *et al.* (1989, 2019) and Iqrasan *et al.* (2017), who found significant differences in aching yield among various sunflower hybrids. This was attributed to an accumulation of growing degree days and photosynthetic, as suggested by Caliskan *et al.* (2008). While sunflowers thrive in relatively warm temperatures, they are sensitive to cold temperatures, according to Brouder *et al.* (2008).

5. Conclusion:

Sunflower hybrids exhibited differential genotypic responses in agro-saline soil conditions. The locally available hybrid Hysun 33 performed appreciably phenotypic ally as well as qualitatively even in problem growing area having brackish underground water during both years of experimentation by producing the highest aching yield (2909.00 and 2333.80 kg ha⁻¹) respectively for the year 2017 and 2018 and produced better seed oil yield (38.68 and 37.00%) in both years respectively. The results of this study indicate that sunflower is moderately tolerant to soil salinity. Therefore, hybrid Hysun 33 can be grown successfully in problem soil of

Southern Punjab (D.G. Khan), Pakistan and hereby recommended among farming community having such type of soil and underground brackish water.

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